

MAKING THE RELIEF BETWEEN THE ROWS OF COTTON COMFORTABLE FOR PLANTING WINTER WHEAT

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the methods of preparing the row spacing for sowing of winter wheat when sowing cotton between rows, and creating the inter-row relief for winter wheat.

As a result, the area under crops and yields of cereals, including winter wheat, has increased. Our country has fully achieved grain independence.

Cotton and winter wheat are grown as the main crops on the irrigated lands of the country. Cotton and grain crops are alternated on farms specializing in cotton and grain growing. At the same time, winter wheat is planted in the areas free of cotton. Every year, the area under winter wheat in the country is 600,000 hectares.

The technology of growing wheat between rows of cotton is drastically different from the technology of growing winter wheat in the open field. There are differences in the cultivation of winter wheat between rows of cotton, not

plowing, leveling, chiseling, and other agrotechnical measures. Therefore, between the rows of cotton, the cultivation of winter wheat saves energy, resources, and the cost of grown grain is relatively low.

There are also disadvantages of sowing winter wheat between rows of cotton. When winter wheat is sown between rows of cotton, the seeds are not evenly distributed, and the seeds in the stalks and stalks germinate at different times and at different thicknesses as they fall to different depths, resulting in plants of different ages and different yields. This has a negative impact on yield and grain quality.

Autumn wheat, harvested from cotton stalks and planted in open fields,

does not have time to accumulate until the winter.

Although winter wheat is planted in large areas between rows, due to the lack of science-based cultivation technology, the yield on many farms does not exceed 30-35 ts / ha. This is due to the lack of science-based cultivation technology and technical means that can overcome the above shortcomings.

There is no special parking system for planting winter wheat between the rows of cotton. Optimizing soil performance before planting, eliminating the above-mentioned shortcomings by evenly distributing the seeds at planting and burying them at the same depth, Development of improved technology and technical means of growing autumn grain among the row of cotton is of great importance in improving grain yield and grain quality. It is important that in the processing of a series, it is important to conveniently plant its relief in line in seeds.

As a result of many years of research held at the Samarkand Agricultural Institute, the Samarkand Agricultural Institute has been created fully meet the above requirements. This device is optimally processed by the cotton plans, and sows the seeds of wheat.

Working organs with flick handholds have been used in the processing section of the proposed device, which smoothes the range of the soil between the IRD. After opening a specially made of the opener, sowing sownets will be placed in the back of the section.

The plane of the profile allows seals to sow the seeds flat among the series. 2 60 cm Smooth rows of softener in the sowing of the 60 cm and a special working body (1), and the special working organs bent in the row of 90 cm (Figure 1 , b) The quality of processing and planting is high when placed in place.

Figure 1. Row between rows 60sm (a) and 90cm (b) processing and planting section. Among the number of working widths after the work section is 90Cm shows in Figure

2.

Figure 2. The profile between the lane 90 cm wide

As we can see from the picture, between the row is formed a flat surface against both sides of the middle. In this area, it will be possible to install three to three parties (60sm, two soshettes and line seeds.

The working section grinds and makes it easier for planting notifying the soil. The crushing rate of soil in the proposed work authorities is given in the table.

Table

Saleric granulation in cases treated with experimental working organs

Processing depth, cm	Recurrence	Agregate dimensions				
		>1 mm	1...2 mm	2...3 mm	3...5 mm	5mm>
		%	%	%	%	%
5	1	28,2	24,4	19,1	15,2	13,1
	2	24,9	22,7	17,9	13,9	20,6
	3	30,1	23,9	13,3	10,6	22,1
10	1	28,6	22,3	18,6	15,1	15,4
	2	26,3	23,7	14,9	9,4	25,7
	3	26,2	22,8	18,6	13,6	18,8
15	1	29,6	19,8	17,6	11,7	21,3
	2	31,1	19,5	18,2	13,4	17,8
	3	35,1	20,6	15,3	8,7	20,3

Conclusion. It should be noted that when the proposed working authorities are treated closely, the relief of the cotton is the opportunity to approach the level of the cotton open, resulting in the opportunity to rent the same depth of wheat seeds.

Working authorities invited in the quality of dusting are also good indicators of traditional working bodies. The development of a device that is processed by these working organs and the quality of seeds for the rape of cotton is an urgent scientific and technical and technical issue.

References:

1. Тошболтаев М.Т., Ким Э. Замонавий техника воситаларидан фойдаланиш самарадорлигини ошириш омиллари: тавсия ва таклифлар. Тошкент: Фан, 2001. 72-бет.

2. Норқулов Э., Тошболтаев М. Т. Ғўза парвариши - дастлабки агротехник тадбирлар // Ўзбекистон қишлоқ хўжалиги. 2007.
3. Шоумарова М, Абдиллаев Т. Қишлоқ хўжалиги машиналари. (Ўрим йиғим ва тозалаш машиналари) Ташкент, “Меҳнат”. 2002.
4. Догода А.П. Обоснование параметров и режимов работ опрыскивателя тунельного типа для виноградников // Дисс. Симферополь, 2017.
5. Shodiev Xodjimurod Baxronovich, Mirzaxodjayeov Sherzodxuja Shoxruxovich Sabzavot mahsulotlarini yetishtirishda ko'chat ekish agregatini asoslash. (Журнал агро процессинг номер 6, выпуск 2, Journal of agro processing volume 6, issue 2). №6 (2020).
6. Shodiev Kh.B., Mamasov A.A., Akhmedov R.T. PLANTING MACHINE WORKING SECTION AND PARAMETERS FOUNDATION. Application of Science for Sustainable Development to Overcome Covid-19 Pandemic (Journal Impact Factor: 7.223, ISSN: 2581-4230, journalnx.com). India. Special Issue No: 9, August, 2020. Page No.: 286-289